

Novel Graphitic Oxynitrides as Photocatalysts for Sustainable H₂ Production and CO₂ Valorization. The Importance of Self-Assembly for Catalytic Activity

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Abstract: The field of carbocatalysis, often portrayed by paradigmatic graphitic carbonaceous structures, has become a booming topic tailored for multiple applications. To this end, a new metal-free carbocatalyst has been constructed from simple prebiotic monomers such as cyanamide and glyoxal. The resulting material shows an excellent performance as photocatalyst for H₂ production and CO₂ valorization, thus unveiling its real value to tackle sustainable goals. The unique oxygen-rich carbonaceous structure has been characterized in detail, which is consistent with a graphitic layered network. The described performance in two major societal concerns along with a facile preparation from C1/C2 platforms, makes this type of overlooked oxynitride carbocatalysts promising for real-life environmental endeavors.

Introduction

It should be unnecessary to underline the pivotal importance of graphitic carbon nitrides, comprising a broad family of layered polymeric materials with diverse dimensionality,^[1,2] which can be employed as efficient (photo)catalysts in synthetic organic transformations^[3] together with highly demanding concerns,^[4] such as clean hydrogen production and CO₂ reduction, among others. Structural variations can be conducted on two major arrangements,^[5,6] namely laminar graphitic carbon nitride (α -C₃N₄) versus the otherwise anticipated adamantane-type network (β -C₃N₄). From a compositional viewpoint, such nitrides can contain significant amount of hydrogen and occlude other saline species,^[7,8] metals,^[9] nanocomposites,^[10] and other heteroatoms.^[11] Heteroatom doping of carbon networks is particularly appealing, not only by introducing active functional

groups on the surface of the material, but also because such a change alters polarity and provides binding sites for adsorption and catalysis. These facts are relevant in oxygen doping leading to a greater disruption of the C_{sp2} framework.^[12] Carbon oxynitrides, irrespective of their molecular decoration, belong clearly to this class, less exploited than ubiquitous carbon nitrides, despite they have proven to be efficient photocatalysts^[13] and metal-free carbocatalysts in synthesis.^[14] The typical preparation of carbon oxynitrides involves the oxidation of carbon nitride precursors.^[13] They are likewise available by covalent coupling of graphitic nitride with graphene oxide,^[15] uracil,^[16] or supramolecular networks generated from melamine and cyanuric acid.^[17] Carbonaceous oxynitrides have also been obtained by thermal treatment of biomass and urea.^[18] Highly ordered nanoporous carbon oxynitride, suitable for Li-batteries, has been prepared from a single CNO precursor (namely, carbonylhydrazide) using silica templates and thermal carbonization.^[19] An atypical carbon-free metal oxynitride (TiO_xN_y) has been recently obtained by nitridation of a sol-gel-based oxide, and employed as photocatalyst for H₂ generation.^[20] Herein, we report on a novel approach starting from simpler monomers and leading to heterocycles bearing endocyclic oxygen and/or nitrogen atoms prone to further elongation reactions. Previous studies have shown that cyanamide and glyoxal, which have been found in astrochemical scenarios, can assemble into complex molecular arrangements,^[21-23] consistent with spectroscopic signatures detected in solar moons and exoplanets. This prompted us to consider such carbonaceous structures as credible potential metal-free catalysts in prebiotic chemistry as well as for current technological pursuits, both in unmodified and physico-chemically modified forms.

Reactions conducted at discrete cyanamide:glyoxal ratios (1:1, 1:2 and 2:1) give rise, under stirring for one week, to extensive oligomerizations (with molecular masses up to 1000), both in aqueous and organic solvents.^[21,22] Under such conditions, however, reactions in acetone do not incorporate the latter into the supramolecular structures. Aqueous condensations using ratios > 2:1 afford insoluble solids upon oligomer aggregation, which presumably involve oligocyanamides and melamine-like triazines.^[23] Both five-membered (oxazolines and imidazolines) and six-membered (morpholines and pyrazines) can be detected by spectroscopic methods (Figure 1) and were predicted by computational calculations as well. Glyoxal plays a catalytic role that enables cyanamide oligomerization toward triazine units.^[23]

Formation of O/N-containing heterocycles ensures that porous and/or lamellar carbonaceous oxynitrides could be generated by calcination. Remarkably, direct calcination of cyanamide:glyoxal mixtures, without previous self-assembly, yields materials with little or no catalytic ability, thus proving that preformed oligomerization is mandatory to achieve suitable solids with catalytic active sites. Herein, we provide a detailed characterization of the resulting solids obtained through wet chemistry and how the pyrolyzed material exhibits good performance for current photocatalytic protocols targeting sustainable energy-efficient inventory production.

Figure 1. Putative oxygen-rich nitrogenated cores present in oligomers after cyanamide:glyoxal condensations. Ratios and water dehydrations are indicated in every case for clarity.

Results and Discussion

Catalyst formation

We began a preliminary screening of carbon oxynitride formation by mixing different cyanamide:glyoxal ratios in acetone, although a 6:1 stoichiometry was found to be satisfactory in terms of product mass and reaction times (see experimental for other ratios). Thus, a solid forms at room temperature and gradually darkens after several days. The existence of oligomeric mixtures hampers the accurate determination of empirical formulas or conventional chemical yields. Mass balances, however, can be interpreted in terms of reaction mass efficiency (RME), which represents a valuable concept in green chemistry metrics.^[24] The latter together with atom economy measures how much of the starting precursors end up in the isolated product. Expressed in percentage, RME is the quotient between the mass of product and the masses of the raw materials; albeit glyoxal, being available as aqueous solution, is denoted as CHO-CHO units. Data gathered in Table 1 show mass profits (RME values) and elemental analyses of solid phases before and after calcination at different temperatures, together with that of the corresponding liquid phase after drying. Average compositions can be fitted to carbon atoms by analogy with standard carbon nitride formula ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$). While calcination at 150 °C for 12 h still provides good RMEs, higher temperatures (350-500 °C for 3 h) decrease significantly the mass efficiency as expected, due to mass losses which may include occluded acetone and water (Table 1, entries 3-5). In all cases, such materials contain appreciable amounts of nitrogen and oxygen, although thermal treatments affect significantly such contents. Carbon percentages increase and hydrogen ones decrease as the calcination temperature increases. On the other hand, calcination at either 150 or 350 °C leads to higher N contents than at 500 °C, whilst rise in oxygen occurs at the latter. These variations suggest molecular reorganization of pristine aggregates formed after mixing, which are otherwise consistent with gas emissions detected by thermogravimetric analyses. At 350 °C, liberation of ammonia is prevalent over those of oxygen-containing species (H_2O , CO_2 and CO). As temperature increases, ammonia emission is substantially halted, while generation of other gases, CO in particular, increases (Figures S1-S19).

XPS analyses (Tables 2 and S6, Figures 2 and S38) corroborated the surface structure of carbon oxynitrides for the solids calcinated. Thus, peaks at 284, 286 and 288 eV in the C1s spectrum (Figure 2b) correspond to C-C, N-CH / C-O and N-C=N bonds, respectively.^[17] Likewise, the N1s spectrum showed one main peak at about 399 eV which is consistent with the presence of C-N=C groups,^[15] and the peak at 532 eV (O1s spectrum, Figure 2d) confirmed the existence of C=O bonds.^[17]

Table 1. Experimental conditions, RME values and compositions of 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal solids.^[a]

Entry	Conditions and RME ^[b]		Elemental analyses (%)				Compositions
	Conditions	RME	C	H	N	O	C ₃ H _x N _y O _z
1	Isolated solid ^[c]	29.0	33.10	4.66	35.30	26.94	C _{3.00} H _{5.08} N _{2.76} O _{1.84}
	Liquid phase ^[d]	39.2	39.80	6.17	38.20	15.83	C _{3.00} H _{5.68} N _{2.51} O _{1.05}
2	At 150 °C ^[e]	92.4	38.50	4.80	43.30	13.40	C _{3.00} H _{4.46} N _{2.53} O _{0.78}
3	At 350 °C ^[f,g]	36.8	40.50	3.51	45.60	10.39	C _{3.00} H _{3.12} N _{2.73} O _{0.55}
4	At 350 °C ^[e,g]	34.8	41.30	3.37	45.90	9.43	C _{3.00} H _{2.93} N _{2.85} O _{0.50}
5	At 500 °C ^[f,g]	34.9	46.40	1.67	34.90	17.03	C _{3.00} H _{1.30} N _{1.94} O _{0.83}

^[a]Glyoxal was employed as 40% aqueous solution. ^[b]Reaction mass efficiency: (mass of product) / (masses of starting materials). ^[c]The solid isolated by room temperature-processing decomposes at 110.9 °C. ^[d]Mother liquors dried in vacuum prior to analysis. ^[e]Calcination in open vessel. ^[f]Calcination in sealed vessel. ^[g]Solid previously calcinated at 150 °C.

Figure 2. XPS analysis of carbon oxynitride from 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal reaction calcinated at 500 °C: a) survey spectrum; b) deconvoluted spectrum of C1s; c) deconvoluted spectrum of N1s; d) deconvoluted spectrum of O1s.

Table 2. Elemental composition of calcinated solids from 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal reactions obtained from XPS.

Temperature	C 1s (%)	N 1s (%)	O 1s (%)	C ₃ N _y O _z
350 °C	54.7	39.4	5.9	C ₃ N _{1.85} O _{0.24}
500 °C	57.8	38.6	3.6	C ₃ N _{1.72} O _{0.14}

Structural characterization

Spectral data provide further clues for surface modification. It is noteworthy the templating assistance of acetone in a slow process involving oligomer formation prior to calcination, a fact not observed in reactions conducted in the same solvent at lower cyanamide:glyoxal ratios, namely 2:1, 1:1 and 1:2.^[21] Since glyoxal can potentially react with four cyanamide units (Figure 1), the latter will be removed from the reaction mixture at lower ratios. ¹³C NMR spectra of residues isolated from mother liquors after drying (Figure 3) show a set of carbon resonances in the shielded zone (65-17 ppm), which are consistent with methylene (65-49 ppm) and methyl (32-17 ppm). Such peaks appear in the ¹³C NMR spectrum of the precipitate as well (Figure S20), although with lower intensities, as hydrophobic alkyl groups increase product solubility in acetone. Peaks observable in the range 130-105 ppm suggest the participation of acetone, presumably via aldol-type condensations, with the exception of quaternary carbons such as cyano (118 ppm) and carbonyls (above 200 ppm). Other quaternary resonances between 170 and 145 ppm can likewise be attributable to C=N groups depicted in Figure 1, while carbon signals between 70 and 45 ppm point to O-CH-N and N-CH-N fragments arising from cyanamide-rich oligomers.^[21-23] Proton NMR recorded for both the isolated solid (Figure S21) and material from liquid phase (Figure S22), exhibit signals characteristic of alkyl groups (between 2.0 and 0.7 ppm) with intensities comparable to those resonating at downfields (9.0-4.3 ppm), thus evidencing a well-organized patterning and growth.

Moreover, comparison of D₂O-exchanged spectra (Figures S23-S24) show a greater proportion of non-exchangeable protons than those of glyoxal.

Solid-state ¹³C CP MAS NMR spectrum (Figure 4) of the solid calcinated at 150 °C exhibits a pattern similar to that measured in solution and supports the significant transformation of starting materials. Thus, two intense peaks at 167.5 and 160.5 ppm are close to carbon resonances observed for triazine structures such as melam at 165 and 167 ppm, melem at 155-156 ppm and 164-166.5 ppm, and melamine between 167.5 and 169.2,^[5d] although neither of them are coincidental in the present oligomers. Spectral data are consistent with the existence of *N*-substituted melam, as a result of glyoxal oligomerization and concomitant (or sequential) reactions with solvent molecules (acetone). Bands that can be assigned with confidence to triazine nuclei at 167.5 and 160.5 ppm lie in the range described for melam by Schnick et al.^[25] However, the observed deshielding relative to reference values could be due to *N*-alkylation of exocyclic amino groups. The latter can also be deduced from resonances around 66, 49 and 42 ppm, attributable to aliphatic carbons linked to either oxygen or nitrogen atoms, together with upfield-shifted peaks near 30 ppm. Even more shielded signals point to alkyl chains devoid of heteroatom bonding. On the other hand, peaks of moderate intensity in the range 116-130 ppm clearly suggest unsaturated carbons, presumably by reaction with acetone as well. Likewise, broad, yet well-defined signals between 33 and 14 ppm evidence the existence of alkyl groups coming from acetone. The appearance of nitrogenated fragments can also be inferred from the signal sets observed in solid-state ¹⁵N NMR spectra (Figure 5). Resonances at -210.1 and -217.6 ppm agree with above-mentioned carbon peaks and can be attributed to tertiary nitrogen atoms of triazine units and other heterocycles. Upper field signals at -240.1 and -249.0 ppm are due to NH groups, while the intense zone centered at -293.4 together with peaks at -317.7 and -329.9 ppm point to NH₂ bonds. Overall, the pattern is similar to that detected for triazine structures.^[5d]

Figure 3. Decoupled ¹³C NMR and DEPT spectra of isolated solid from mother liquors after drying (Table 1, entry 1) recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ solution.

Figure 4. Solid-state ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the isolated solid calcinated at 150 °C (Table 1, entry 2).

Figure 5. Solid-state ^{15}N NMR spectrum of the isolated solid calcinated at 150 °C (Table 1, entry 2).

Also, FT-IR spectra have diagnostic value for monitoring the structural variations as the thermal treatment increases (Figures S25-S27). Calcination at 150 °C results in a material showing sharp stretching bands ($3500\text{-}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributable to OH and NH bands. Calcination at 350 °C changes the aforementioned bands to a broad absorption centered at 3446 cm^{-1} , while at 500 °C the bands convert into an absorption continuum. Peaks at or close to 3470 and 3330 cm^{-1} can be attributed to stretching of NH_2 group.^[5d,25-27] The former decreases in intensity along the series melamine, melam, melam, melom, and melom, and both bands decrease or completely disappear at high temperatures ($>500\text{ °C}$), which can be due to deamination reactions.^[5e,28,29] The intense band observed at 3470 cm^{-1} in melam hydrate has been assigned to OH stretching in H-bonded water molecules.^[25] Absorptions around 3000 cm^{-1} are in line with typical CH bond stretching, although strong H-bonded NH and OH groups cannot be ruled out, as such associations shift stretching towards lower wavenumbers. The band observed at 1634 cm^{-1} in material calcinated at 350 °C can be due to bending of primary amino (NH_2) groups, as similar bands at 1650 and 1625 cm^{-1} have been detected in melamine.^[27]

and at 1632 cm^{-1} in melom.^[25] Melom exhibits intense peaks at 1612 and 1464 cm^{-1} , while the present solids show broad absorptions between 1600 and 1300 cm^{-1} after calcination at 150 °C and 350 °C. Further evolution takes place at 500 °C, leading to intense broadening between 1000 and 1200 cm^{-1} . In general, thermal treatment leads to a substantial decrease in solubility, and spectral data in solution could not be collected for samples calcinated at 350 and 500 °C.

Mass spectra (ESI experiments) recorded on the precipitate and the solid isolated from the mother liquors, allowed us to assess the wide range of oligomeric species generated by condensation of cyanamide and glyoxal with extrusion of ammonia and water molecules (Table S1). The sequential oligomerization of cyanamide into dicyandiamide and melamine-like analogs is most likely assisted by glyoxal-containing structures,^[21-23] leading to primary heterocycles such as those depicted in Figure 1. The model accounts for reaction of acetone and cyanamide or products thereof. In fact, the direct condensation of cyanamide and acetone was reported long time ago leading presumably to cyano-pyrimidine derivatives.^[30] Likewise, formation of 2-aminopyrimidines arise from reacting cyanamide and β -dicarbonyl compounds.^[31]

UV-Vis spectra of cyanamide-glyoxal oligomers displayed maxima at 215-218 nm. Carbon oxynitrides from cyanamide:glyoxal reactions calcinated at 150 °C showed maxima at 205 nm with estimated energy band gaps of about 5 eV (Figures S28-S33).

In order to evaluate the stability of the as-prepared oxynitrides against leaching, samples calcinated at different temperatures were successively suspended in water within a 72-h interval (Table 3), and determining the total organic carbon (TOC) contents in every case. Data reflect considerable lixiviation for the oxynitride calcinated at 150 °C, whereas a substantial decrease, with little or almost negligible carbon loss, was observed for samples treated at 350 °C and 500 °C, thus evidencing their greater stability.

Table 3. Lixiviation of carbon oxynitride samples after reaction and calcination.^[a]
b)

Temperature (°C)	mg TOC / g cat (24 h)	mg TOC / g cat (48 h)	mg TOC / g cat (72 h)
150	142.80	140.89	120.31
350	1.897	1.692	0.958
500	1.105	1.090	0.575

^[a]Catalyst from cyanamide:glyoxal (6:1) ratio after reaction in acetone and calcination. ^[b]TOC determined by catalytic combustion analysis.

Solid stability can also be inferred from morphological evolution through SEM analyses (Figure 6). Particle agglomeration along a broad scale range is observed, from a few μm to large particles with diameters of ca. $500\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Image acquisition was problematic for samples calcinated at 150 and 350 °C as morphologies were sensitive to electron beam exposure, whereas the pattern

remained unaffected for samples calcinated at 500 °C. Surface roughness increases as the calcination temperature increases as well. Likewise, transmission microscopy (TEM) evidences the formation of lamellar aggregates (Figure 7).

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of carbon oxynitrides (from 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal reactions) calcinated at different temperatures (from top to bottom): 150 °C (scale bars: 100 μm and 1 μm), 350 °C (scale bars: 100 μm and 100 nm), and 500 °C (scale bars: 100 μm and 100 nm).

Figure 7. TEM micrographs showing lamellar particles of carbon oxynitrides (from 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal reaction) calcinated at 500 °C.

Powder XR diffractograms show a main peak centered around 27° (2θ value). The peak is indicative of stacking in aromatic conjugated systems, and consistent with the (002) peak of graphitic materials. By increasing the calcination temperature, the peak becomes more intense, thereby pointing to a higher concentration of aromatic groups and stacked planes, or in other words a more ordered graphitic structure. It is noteworthy that for the sample simply involving reagent mixing followed by calcination, without prior oligomerization under agitation (for 7 days), the peak in question is considerably less intense, and therefore indicating a less extended graphitic structure (Figure 8). Another less intense peak, indexed as (001), is detected above 10°, resulting from the periodic order of condensed s-triazine units in the layers.^[32]

Figure 8. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of cyanamide-glyoxal samples (6:1 ratio). From top to bottom: (a) calcinated at 350 °C, (b) calcinated at 500 °C, (c) cyanamide-glyoxal mixture calcinated at 500 °C without previous oligomerization reaction for 7 days under stirring and (d) calcinated at 150 °C.

Photocatalytic activity

In view of the aforementioned structural features pointing to a layered heterocyclic array with high surface area (23 m²/g vs 15 m²/g of cyanamide-based *g*-C₃N₄, determined by BET isotherms, Figures S34 and S39), we envisaged the potentiality of this carbon oxynitride as heterogeneous photocatalyst. Thus, in a preliminary test, photoirradiation of catalyst-containing glycerol suspension under constant stirring (see Experimental) led to H₂ production (Figure 9). The material calcinated at 150 °C lacked catalytic activity. However, material calcinated at 500 °C exhibited superior performance than that of 350 °C. Moreover, the preorganized catalyst obtained by reaction of cyanamide and glyoxal in acetone after one week, using 6:1 molar ratio, was more efficient than solids generated at different concentrations. This suggests an optimal self-assembled structure achieved by chemical reaction of the three components prior to thermal treatment.

Figure 9. Comparative estimation of H₂ production from glycerol using carbon oxynitride as photocatalyst under different experimental conditions.

The plot shown in Figure 10 also evidences a greater hydrogen liberation over time when using the oxynitride calcinated at 500

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°C, with respect to a typical *g*-C₃N₄ phase prepared by pyrolysis of cyanamide at the same temperature.^[32] A series of reasonable surmises accounts for this finding. Previous cross-assembly involving glyoxal and acetone molecules, together with gas extrusion after thermal treatment, should lead to enhanced porosity and creation of supplemental catalytic sites with oxygen-containing functional groups. Even if an ideal 2D structure cannot be established, powder X-ray diffraction data indicates a graphite-like layered material (Figure 8).

Figure 10. Comparative estimation of H₂ production from glycerol using carbon oxynitride or cyanamide-based carbon nitride as photocatalysts.

Carbon sequestration via CO₂ valorization is clearly another key challenge in sustainable pursuits. A common strategy involves the use of organic pollutants as sacrificial agents. To this end, metoprolol (MTP), a selective β-blocker that represents a pharmaceutical pollutant in wastewater, was employed in aqueous solution (50 ppm). Photoirradiation of that solution containing the oxynitride under stirring and constant bubbling of CO₂ flow decreased gradually the concentration of MTP over time, as measured by HPLC analyses, from 50 ppm (initial concentration) to 22 ppm using a 6:1 cyanamide:glyoxal catalyst (see Figure 11). Total organic carbon values reflect the remaining organic components in solution, as it is higher than the remaining MTP concentration. Further analysis by HPLC-UV reveals the conversion of organic sacrificial agent and/or CO₂ to formic acid (Figure S36). Actually, the aforementioned catalyst calcined at 500 °C achieved 35% selectivity to formic acid. Again, CO₂ consumption was almost negligible for oxynitrides obtained at 150 °C.

The use of carbon nitrides to produce H₂ (often by water splitting) and to reduce CO₂ (with and without sacrificial organic agents) has been extensively documented,^[33] although the specific use of a CO₂ atmosphere is seldom reported. Carbon nitrides show photocatalytic activity on reducing CO₂ in the presence of water, leading selectively to CO.^[34] Catalyst's modification enables to fine-tune CO₂ reduction to other end products of industrial importance,^[35] especially CH₃OH,^[36] CH₄,^[37] or HCO₂H.^[38]

Figure 11. Comparative degradation of metoprolol [MTP] using CO₂ as atmosphere at 2 and 6 hours. (blue and orange bars). Total organic carbon (TOC) after 6 hours of reaction (secondary axis, gray line).

Conclusion

In summary, this study discloses a new type of metal-free heterogeneous organocatalyst that can be obtained from cyanamide and glyoxal after reaction in acetone. This chemical pre-treatment ensures the formation of an assembled network, whose hypothetical structure should contain heterocyclic oligomers with reactive nitrogen and oxygen end groups. In the absence of chemical organization before calcination, the pyrolyzed material lacks catalytic activity. The ability of the resulting carbon oxynitride as photocatalyst has been demonstrated through efficient hydrogen production from glycerol, as well as CO₂ valorization using an organic pollutant as sacrificial reagent. In both cases, good and promising results have been obtained with respect to conventional graphitic carbon nitride. Further work is under way to explore the catalytic properties of doped structures. In addition, and given the low toxicity and safety of cyanamide and glyoxal mixtures, their potentiality as soil fertilizers is in progress.

Experimental Section

Self-assembly procedure prior to calcination

To a solution of cyanamide (5.0 g, 119.0 mmol) in acetone (25 mL) was added glyoxal (40% aqueous solution, 2.30 mL, 19.8 mmol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature. An initially formed reddish precipitate darkens gradually under such conditions. After 7 days, the black solid was isolated by filtration, washed with acetone and dried under vacuum. The mother liquors were evaporated, and the resulting residue subjected to further analysis. Table 4 summarizes the masses of precipitates and solid isolated from the mother liquors, and the corresponding mass efficiencies for different compositions.

Table 4. Reactions of cyanamide and glyoxal at different stoichiometries.¹

Molar ratio	Glyoxal (mmol)	Solids		Liquid phase ^[b]	RME ^[c]
		Mass (g)	DP (°C) ^[a]		
3:1	39.7	3.2023	118.2	2.9728	84.9 %
6:1	19.8	1.7861	110.9	2.4178	68.2%
12:1	9.9	1.1432	116.3	5.5926	119.0%
24:1	5.0	0.7831	135.0	3.7938	86.3%

^[a]Temperature of sample decomposition. ^[b]Mother liquors after drying.

^[c]Reaction mass efficiency: (mass of product) / (masses of starting materials), not considering acetone.

Typical carbocatalyst formation procedure

To a solution of cyanamide (5.0 g, 119.0 mmol) in acetone (25 mL) was added glyoxal (40% aqueous solution) with stirring at room temperature. After 7 d, the reaction mixture was evaporated, and the resulting residue was dried at 150 °C for 12 h. The resulting residue was calcinated at different temperatures (350 and 500 °C) for 3 h using a muffle furnace.

For comparative assessment, other materials without self-assembly, i.e. by mixing the starting precursors only, were obtained as follows:

- To a solution of cyanamide (5.0 g, 119.0 mmol) in acetone (25 mL) was added glyoxal (40% aqueous solution, 19.8 mmol). After homogenization for a few minutes, the reaction mixture was evaporated, and the resulting residue was dried at 150 °C for 12 h. The as-obtained material was calcinated at 500 °C for 3 h using a muffle furnace.
- Cyanamide (5.0 g, 119.0 mmol) was added to glyoxal (40% aqueous solution, 19.83 mmol). After homogenization, the reaction mixture was evaporated and the residue dried at 150 °C for 12 h. The corresponding material was calcinated at 500 °C for 3 h using a muffle furnace.
- Graphitic carbon nitride (*g*-C₃N₄), employed as comparative reference, was prepared by pyrolysis of cyanamide in a muffle furnace according to the method described in the literature.^[32]

Solid characterization

Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy in attenuated total reflectance mode (ATR-FTIR) analyses were performed on a Nicolet is10 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). Sampling resolution was set at 4 cm⁻¹ and 32 scans from 560 to 4000 cm⁻¹ wavenumber range. Spectra were processed using Thermo Scientific Omnic 3.2.v software. UV-Vis spectra were measured on a Thermo 201 spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrometers (at 400 or 500 MHz, and 100 or 125 MHz for ¹H and ¹³C nuclei, respectively) in DMSO-*d*₆ and D₂O solutions. Assignments were facilitated by DEPT (Distortionless Enhancement by Polarization Transfer) experiments.

Thermogravimetric analyses/differential thermal analyses (TGA/DTA) were carried out in air (50 mL min⁻¹) from 50 °C to 1000 °C (heating rate at 10 °C/min) with a thermobalance STA 449 F3 Jupiter-Netzsch. The average sample weight was ca. 10 mg with a resolution of ±0.02 µg. The instrument was calibrated (for both temperature and weight by standard methods). Microanalyses (C, H, N) were determined on a Leco® CHNS628 analyzer. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed with on a FlexPS-ARPES-E equipment from SPECS with monochromatic K α Al radiation (1486.68 eV), 15 KV voltage, and 6.6 mA current.

The porous structure of the catalysts was assessed by nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms acquired at -196 °C in a Quantachrome Autosorb iQ2-C Series apparatus. Before analysis, samples were outgassed at 150 °C for 10 h under a residual pressure < 10⁻² mbar. For CO₂ isotherms, samples were outgassed at 200 °C for 24 h. The BET equation and t-plot method were applied to determine surface area and pore volume.

The morphology and composition of the catalyst particles were examined by scanning electron microscopy fitted to energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) using a Hitachi S-4800 apparatus working at 20–30 kV accelerating voltage and 500–2000 magnification.

TEM Tecnai G2 20 Twin transmission electron microscope (FEI Company) operated at 200 kV was employed to evaluate the crystallinity and morphology of samples. Interplanar distances of different crystalline particles were obtained with Image J (NIH) software.

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of cyanamide-glyoxal samples were obtained in the 2 θ range = 10–80° with a step size of 0.01° and 0.5 s of sampling per point using a powder Bruker D8 Advance XRD diffractometer with Cu K α 1 radiation (λ = 1.5406 Å) and a linear detector VANTEC (with 3° aperture).

Electrospray ionization mass spectra (ESI-MS) were analyzed using a 6520 Accurate-Mass Q-TOF LC/MS instrument with DUAL ESI interface (Agilent Technologies) coupled to an Agilent 1200 Liquid Chromatography (LC) apparatus. All solids were kept in a vacuum desiccator for at least 48 h prior to analysis. A solution of oligomers (5 mg) in water (1000 mL) was then introduced in the system using injector and column switching valve directly to the interface. The mobile phase was milli-Q water containing 1.0% acetic acid with a flow at 0.3 mL/min. The acid imparts a positive charge on some functional groups; all samples were run in positive scan mode only. Mass spectra were recorded from 40 to 1000 *m/z* values in high-resolution mode (at 4 GHz, ADC rate for data acquisition) and real-time processing on the mass peaks detected in each transient, weighting the apex data much more heavily than the shoulders. Conditions in the nebulizer were 350 °C (gas temperature), with a flow rate of 6 mL/min and 60 psi.

Lixiviation stability tests

In order to determine the stability towards lixiviation, solid samples (0.2 g) were suspended in ultrapure water (100 mL) and stirred at 50 rpm in a by-ven machine thermostabilized at 25 °C. Aliquots (10 mL) were taken after 24, 48 and 72 h to measure the amount

of total organic carbon (TOC) by catalytic combustion on a TOC-V CSH apparatus (Shimadzu).

Catalytic activity

All experiments were conducted with the as-formed oxynitride materials without any metal or organic additive as cocatalyst. Solids were tested in the photocatalytic production of hydrogen from glycerol. All reactions were carried out in a Penn Photoreactor m2, utilizing LED light radiation at a wavelength of 450 nm and an intensity of 325 mW/cm². In each experiment, the photocatalyst (1 g/L) was suspended in a 10% (v/v) glycerol solution (5 mL) and irradiated for 30 minutes under stirring. To maintain an inert atmosphere, the solution was continuously purged with argon at a flow rate of 4 mL/min and the gas composition of this flow (H₂ and CO₂) was on-line analyzed using a gas chromatograph apparatus (Agilent Technologies model 7890A) equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and a Supelco CarboxenTM 1010 Plot Column.

For water pollutant degradation with CO₂, the solids were suspended in a 50 ppm solution of metoprolol (100 mL). These reactions were carried out in a 250-mL three-neck round flask with a CO₂ flow of 5 mL/min. After 30 minutes under stirring, light was switched on using Suntest CPS+ solar box (Atlas Material Testing Technology LLC) equipped with a 1500 W air-cooled Xe lamp. The overall irradiance ($\lambda = 300\text{--}800\text{ nm}$) at the photoreactor level was measured with a UV-Vis spectroradiometer (Black Comet C, StellarNet Inc.) resulting in 581.4 W/m². At certain times, samples were withdrawn from the reactor, filtered with 0.45 μm PVDF, and then refrigerated for subsequent analysis. These were conducted on an HPLC apparatus equipped with a UV-Vis detector set at 225 nm (HP 1100 Series chromatograph, Agilent Technologies). A Kromasil C-18 column (5 μm , 150 mm length, 4 mm diameter) was used as the stationary phase while the mobile phase was a mixture of ortho-phosphoric acid in ultrapure water (0.1% v/v, solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B) at a constant flow rate of 1 mL/min. TOC was analyzed by catalytic combustion on a TOC-V CSH apparatus (Shimadzu). Quantification was achieved through with calibration curves with selectivity calculated as:

$$\text{Selectivity (\%)} = (\text{mol formic acid} / \text{mol metoprolol}) * 100$$

Supporting Information

Supporting information for this article is available on the WWW under <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.xxxxxxxx>

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